

**SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE IMAGE
OF THE COMMANDER IN THE INTERPRETATION
OF FOREIGN PSYCHOLOGISTS**

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ANNOTATION

The provided article devoted the social-psychological characteristics of image of military servant, it includes the system of defense, professional, scientific, psychological preparation. The meaning of given article illustrates the conceptual foundations of behavioral, spiritual, emotional, and social-psychological components of image of military servants. That is why, the role of image in activity of military servants, military role, military rank, psychological image, as well as the notion of person also did not stay out of research.

Key words: Commander, military servant, military part, military regulations, military image, social-psychological image, military role, military rank, military professional, military psychologist, military activity, professional patriotism.

States are able to reliably protect the inviolability of their borders, territorial integrity, peace and quiet life of citizens, are equipped with modern weapons and equipment, are mature specialists of their profession, military professionals and fully meet the requirements of today, any armed conflicts that arise in an extreme situation. training of military personnel who can prevent.

In this regard, in recent years, large-scale work has been carried out in our country to consistently reform and develop our national army, strengthen our country's defense capabilities, and train military personnel.

This encourages specialists in the field of psychology to find new solutions for deepening scientific research on the creation and improvement of the socio-psychological concept of the leader's image in the system of the Ministry of Defense.

First of all, it is important to determine the stages of the emergence and development of the problem of image formation in the theoretical and practical processes of the conducted research. In this case, a comprehensive analysis of available sources in philosophy, psychology, pedagogy and a number of research works on the subject is important. So, in our research, we try to analyze the phenomenon of the image and its definition, the psychological components of

the image, the socio-psychological, sociological, cultural-historical and scientific-theoretical foundations in the development of its formation in a chronological system.

First of all, we can divide the history of the emergence, formation and development of the image into three conditional periods based on the scientific views of the theoretician scientist E.V.Yakovlev:

- 1) historical period (9th-7th millennium BC-XVIII century);
- 2) systematization (regulation) period (mid-18th-20th centuries);
- 3) the information age (the middle of the 20th century to the present time)[1].

The first expert on the phenomenon of the image is recognized by the priest Aaron (1445 BC), assistant to the ruler Moisei. Because of Moses' stuttering, Aaron had to speak in his place before the people. For this reason, he was called the ruler's mouthpiece and prophet[2].

The concept of "image" has been formed and developed over the centuries. According to Aristotle (384-322 BC), the famous thinker of antiquity, it is possible to convince the audience only by gaining their goodwill and inclination[3]. The great orator Cicero (106-43 BC), statesman and politician of ancient Rome, emphasized the importance of studying the psychology, interests and tastes of the masses. According to him, the task of the orator is to appeal to the audience aesthetically, to influence their morals and will. A political figure and general, Julius Caesar (102-44 BC) had a brilliant ability to influence the masses. He gained public support through his speeches and stage performances before military battles.

Human history proves that image formation includes various methods, methods and factors that have been effective for centuries. In addition to oratory skills, symbols, various attributes of the image (clothes, smells, decoration, gestures, facial expressions, etc.) Based on historical sources, we can say that the principles of public influence were widely used in preparing for battles, in the process of political elections, in marketing products, in raising funds, in publicizing people and events.

Political scientist N. Machiavelli (1469-1527 years) was considered one of the first theorists of image, and he had a high level of "image sense" or high "image thinking". The important part of such thinking was to think and influence in the interpersonal space, to predict the behavior of the people around, to be able to establish warm relations with people [4].

Researchers I.Nefedov and E.Vlasov say that image is the image of a person in the eyes of people, and gives the most basic interpretation of image [5].

In our opinion, G. Andreeva's interpretation objectively reflects the nature of the image as a socio-psychological phenomenon: "An image is a special image of a perceptual phenomenon. That is why the imaginary image of an object or event is created on the basis of emotional appeals"[6].

Scientific researcher D.Yager includes personal external data in addition to socio-psychological characteristics. He writes that the image is a unique set of external appearance, speech, and behavior. Image is the art of "impression management" [7]. Therefore, the image is understood not only as a visual image, but also as a form and content of internal and external integrity.

Lieutenant General V.Serebryannikov writes in this regard: "The image created by the state regarding the army has great social power. The correct implementation of the work raises the image of the state, instills respect for the army and trust in military personnel, ensures cohesion of the military and citizens, and increases the respect of the population for military service. In a word, it strengthens the security of the army and the country in every way"[8]. Therefore, it is clear from the given classifications that the image of the army cannot be created in a short period of time, but it has sufficient historical foundations and is constantly developing.

Therefore, it requires regular research until a positive image is sufficiently created at each facility of the Armed Forces. It should be noted that the image of the army is formed on the basis of the promotion of its separate districts, formations, military units and units, as well as all types of commanders, officers, non-commissioned sergeants and private soldiers, as well as conscripts (soldiers).

How to determine the practical importance of the image of the Armed Forces or what indicators should be used to describe it? For this, it is necessary to take into account the following main factors:

first, the increase in the number of people serving in the army;
secondly, the expression of a benevolent attitude towards the army among the country's population;
thirdly, the high level of satisfaction of military personnel of different categories with their profession.

In the studies devoted to the military direction, many military specialties have been studied to a certain extent, and socio-professional descriptions and professional applications have been developed. However, these works did not pay attention to the individual qualities, psychophysiological and social characteristics (ethnoculture, gender, age, etc.) of the holder of the profession,

but only the level of professional competence, that is, the aspects within the framework of the "person-profession" system, were taken into account.

Military professions have their own character and tendency, in which the characteristics of the military personnel have a special place, and we can distinguish them into four groups:

- 1) general qualities of a military serviceman;
- 2) qualities of a military serviceman as a specialist;
- 3) combat qualities of a military serviceman;
- 4) service-duty qualities of a military specialist.

In short, the socio-psychological study of the image of the leader-commander in the system of the Ministry of Defense includes a number of positive aspects such as military image, professional competence, military professionalism, professional image, military duty, discipline, patience, courage, combat readiness, psychological preparation, altruism it is possible to justify the extent to which qualities are formed in military personnel.

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